

ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan

Version 2

Description

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally. Various data sets, including ultrasound images from five clinical studies will be collected during the ThrombUS+. This document serves as the Data Management Plan for all these data sets.

ThrombUS+ project:

Grant Agreement: 101137227

Start date: January 1st, 2024

End date: June 30th, 2027

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

ThrombUS+: Wearable
Continuous Point-of-Care
Monitoring, Risk Estimation
and Prevention for Deep Vein
Thrombosis
(corda_____he::101137227)

Researchers

Stylianos Didaskalou (orcid:0000-0001-5932-9626)

Organizations

VDE VERBAND DER ELEKTROTECHNIK ELEKTRONIK
INFORMATIONSTECHNIK EV, ECHONOUS INC, MEDEA SRL,
Technologija, Kaunas University of Technology, TAMPEREEN
KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR, Athena Research and Innovation
Center In Information Communication & Knowledge
Technologies, COMFTECH SRL, SCIGEN TECHNOLOGIES ANONYMI
ETAIREIA PARAGOGIS LOGISMIKOU KAI
ILEKTROMICHANOLOGIKON KATASKEUON, Fraunhofer Institute
for Photonic Microsystems, UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE
TELEMED, FONDAZIONE CASA SOLLIEVO DELLA SOFFERENZA,
VERMON SA, PHAZE KLINIKI EREVNA & FARMAKEFTIKES
SYMVOULES ANONYMI ETAIREIA, PREDICTBY RESEARCH AND

CONSULTING S.L., Lithuanian University of Health Sciences,
GROUPEMENT HOSPITALIER EAUBONNE MONTMORENCY
SIMONE VEIL, GENIKO NOSOKOMEIO PAPAGEORGIOU, MEDIS
MEDIZINISCHE MESSTECHNIK GMBH

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan](#)

Description:

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally. Various data sets, including ultrasound images from five clinical studies will be collected during the ThrombUS+. This document serves as the Data Management Plan for all these data sets.

ThrombUS+ project:

Grant Agreement: 101137227

Start date: January 1st, 2024

End date: June 30th, 2027

Researchers:

[Stylios Didaskalou \(orcid:0000-0001-5932-9626\)](#)

Organizations:

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[MEDEA SRL](#)

[Technologija, Kaunas University of Technology](#)

[TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR](#)

Athena Research and Innovation Center In Information Communication & Knowledge Technologies

COMFTECH SRL

SCIGEN TECHNOLOGIES ANONYMI ETAIREIA PARAGOGIS LOGISMIKOU KAI

ILEKTROMICHANOLOGIKON KATASKEUON

Fraunhofer Institute for Photonic Microsystems

UZDAROJI AKCINE BENDROVE TELEMED

FONDAZIONE CASA SOLLIEVO DELLA SOFFERENZA

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PHAZE KLINIKI EREVNA & FARMAKEFTIKES SYMVOULES ANONYMI ETAIREIA

PREDICTBY RESEARCH AND CONSULTING S.L.

Lithuanian University of Health Sciences

GROUPEMENT HOSPITALIER EAUBONNE MONTMORENCY SIMONE VEIL

GENIKO NOSOKOMEIO PAPAGEORGIOU

MEDIS MEDIZINISCHE MESSTECHNIK GMBH

Contact: Didaskalou Stylianos (stelios.didaskalou@athenarc.gr)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: ThrombUS+: Wearable Continuous Point-of-Care Monitoring, Risk Estimation and Prevention for Deep Vein Thrombosis (corda_____he::101137227)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study C2 Dataset: Evaluation reports by patients and healthcare personnel collected from patients recovering from orthopaedics surgery via the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype

Ultrasound image/video sets, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, lower limb activity and evaluation reports collected from patients recovering from orthopaedics surgery via the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Data sets from 200 patients are planned.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb via conventional ultrasound and the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

- DICOM images/video and related data.
- Anonymized images/video in commonly used format (e.g. tiff).
- Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.
- Anonymized physiological signals from activity sensors, electrical impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography (csv, gdf).

Processed data sets will include:

- Anonymized images and videos in a lossless commonly used format (e.g. tiff).
- Anonymized physiological signals from activity sensors, electrical impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography (csv, gdf).
- Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.
- Image/video labeling data in JSON format.
- Signal labelling data in JSON format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

>40GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief

of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

- Deep vein thrombosis
- Ultrasound images
- ultrasound video
- electrical impedance plethysmography
- light reflection rheography
- activity measurements
- lower limb

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

To be decided

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API.

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Internet connection and a browser.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

The ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

To be decided.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

5000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Eleni Kaldoudi (orcid: [0000-0002-6054-4961](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6054-4961))

ThrombUS+ Coordinator

Role: High level management of the data set.

b. Stylianos Didaskalou (orcid: [0000-0001-5932-9626](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5932-9626))

ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set.

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

None.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Other

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary

- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Yes

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A Dataset: Conventional ultrasound image/video sets collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT of lower limb.

Ultrasound images and video clips collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Finally image/video data is accompanying by the output of labelling by experts to identify structures relevant to DVT diagnosis. Data sets from 3000 patients (with or without DVT) are planned.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during routine conventional ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

- DICOM images/video and related data
- Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.

Processed data sets will include:

- Anonymized images and videos in a lossless commonly used format (e.g. tiff).
- Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary
- Image/video labeling data in JSON format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200GB or more

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

- Training AI models
- Use for training and science awareness via open data challenge

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely:

1. Tampere University Hospital (Finland),

2. Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania),
3. Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece),
4. Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and
5. Simon Veil Hospital (France).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

1. DataCite Schema for data description.
2. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records.
3. ICD, International Classification of Diseases.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

- a. https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf
- b. <https://www.snomed.org/>
- c. <https://icd.who.int/en/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing, and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Deep vein thrombosis, ultrasound image, ultrasound video, lower limb.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

If the dataset is larger than 200 GB (which is the upper limit for Zenodo in extraordinary cases, 50 GB normally), data will be split or other infrastructure will be considered (e.g. paid option in FigShare <https://figshare.com/>)

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

To be decided

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Zenodo

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Internet connection and a browser

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Open

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Idefinitely

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records
<https://www.snomed.org/>

ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
- CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Promote via data challenges.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

5000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Eleni Kaldoudi (orcid: [0000-0002-6054-4961](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6054-4961))

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Role: High level management of the data set

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ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Yes

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B1 Dataset: Ultrasound image/video sets collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT of lower limb via the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.

Ultrasound images and video clips collected from patients referred on suspicion of DVT via the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Finally image/video data is accompanying by the output of labelling by experts to identify structures relevant to DVT diagnosis. Data sets from 500 patients (with or without DVT) are planned.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Diagnostic medical images and videos collected during ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT of the lower limb via the ThrombUS+ ultrasound component.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

- Anonymized images/video in commonly used format (e.g. tiff).
- Raw data from ultrasound probe in proprietary format.
- Patient demographics, biometrics, and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.

Processed data sets will include:

- Anonymized images and videos in a lossless commonly used format (e.g. tiff).
- Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.
- Image/video labelling data in JSON format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

40GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To develop a product
- Other

Training AI models.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from patients referred for an ultrasound scan on suspicion of DVT in the respective department of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

DataCite Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

- DVT
- Deep vein thrombosis
- Ultrasound images

- ultrasound video
- lower limb

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

If the dataset is larger than 200 GB (which is the upper limit for Zenodo in extraordinary cases, 50 GB normally), data will be split or other infrastructure will be considered (e.g. paid option in FigShare <https://figshare.com/>).

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Other

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

to be decided

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API.

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Internet connection and a browser.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

The ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

To be decided

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

To be decided.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

5000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Eleni Kaldoudi (orcid: [0000-0002-6054-4961](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6054-4961))

ThrombUS+ Coordinator

Role: High level management of the data set.

b. Stylianos Didaskalou (orcid: [0000-0001-5932-9626](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5932-9626))

ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Other

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Yes

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study C1 Dataset: Evaluation reports by patients and healthcare personnel collected from patients recovering from orthopaedics surgery via the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype.

Ultrasound image/video sets, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, lower limb activity and evaluation reports collected from patients recovering from orthopaedics surgery via the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype. The dataset also contains patient demographics, biometrics and related medical history data and diagnosis. Data sets from 50 patients are planned.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Diagnostic medical images and videos, light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography, and activity collected from patient recovering from surgery.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

- Anonymized images/video in commonly used format (e.g. tiff).
- Light reflection rheography, electrical impedance plethysmography and activity signals (csv, gdf).
- Patient demographics, biometrics and medical history in JSON format, including mappings to SNOMED-CT, ICD-11, and any other appropriate medical terminology or vocabulary.
- Patient/personnel evaluation reports (txt, pdf).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from patients recovering from orthopaedic surgery in the respective clinics of the 5 participating hospitals in ThrombUS+ consortium, namely Tampere University Hospital (Finland), Lithuanian University of Health Science (Lithuania), Papageorgiou General Hospital (Greece), Home Relief of Suffering

Hospital (Italy), and Simon Veil Hospital (France).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

DataCite Schema for data description,
https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records,
<https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases,
<https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description,
https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

- Deep vein thrombosis
- Ultrasound images
- ultrasound video
- electrical impedance plethysmography
- light reflection rheography
- activity measurements

- lower limb

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

To be decided.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API.

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Internet connection and a browser.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Indefinitely.Assembly.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, <https://www.snomed.org/>. ICD, International Classification of Diseases, <https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf. Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

To be decided.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

To be decided.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

5000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Eleni Kaldoudi (orcid: [0000-0002-6054-4961](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6054-4961))

ThrombUS+ Coordinator

Role: High level management of the data set

b. Stylianos Didaskalou (orcid: [0000-0001-5932-9626](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5932-9626))

ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

None

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Other

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Yes

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B2 Dataset: Lower limb activity measurements collected via wearable sensors and video cameras from normal volunteers.

Lower limb activity measurements via wearable inertial measurement units (IMUs) and video cameras with a set of labels for each measurement including participants demographics, collected from 60 healthy volunteers.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Lower limb activity data from healthy volunteers while performing common physiotherapy exercises in lying, sitting and standing positions.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

- Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via commercial inertial measurement units (IMUs) (.csv, .txt).
- Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4).
- Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference).

Processed data sets will include:

- Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via commercial inertial measurement units (IMUs) (.csv, .txt).
- Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4).
- Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference) (.csv, .txt).

Signal labelling data in JSON format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Less than 15GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To develop a product
- Other

Training AI models.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from healthy volunteers in Democritus University of Thrace and the ATHENA RC.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

DataCite's Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description,

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records,

<https://www.snomed.org/>.

ICD, International Classification of Diseases,

<https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Deep Vein Thrombosis, Lower Limb Activity Data, Physiotherapy Exercises, Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs).

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

To be decided.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API.

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Internet connection and a browser.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

The ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description,

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records,

<https://www.snomed.org/>.

ICD, International Classification of Diseases,

<https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

DataCite Schema for data description,

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

To be decided.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

To be decided.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator

Role: High level management of the data set .

Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set .

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B3 Dataset: Lower limb activity measurements collected via prototype wearable sensors and video cameras from normal volunteers.

Lower limb activity measurements via prototype inertial measurement unit (IMU) based sensors and video cameras with a set of labels for each measurement including participants demographics, collected from 10 healthy volunteers.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Reference or canonical

Lower limb activity data from prototype IMU-based system, with video reference, from healthy volunteers while performing common physiotherapy exercises in lying, sitting and standing positions.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Data collected will comprise of:

- Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via prototype inertial measurement units (IMU) based system (.csv, .txt, .gdf). Data will include time (ms), acceleration (m/s²), angular velocity (rad/s) and quaternions (w, x, y and z).
- Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4).
- Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference).

Processed data sets will include:

- Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via custom inertial measurement units (IMU) based system (.csv, .txt, .gdf). Data will include time (ms), acceleration (m/s²), angular velocity (rad/s) and quaternions (w, x, y and z).
- Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4).
- Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference) (.csv, .txt).

Signal labelling data in JSON format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Less than 5GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

- To develop a product
- To improve a product
- Other

To improve and validate limb segment orientation estimation algorithms.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from healthy volunteers in Democritus University of Thrace and ATHENA RC.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description,

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records,

<https://www.snomed.org/>.

ICD, International Classification of Diseases,

<https://icd.who.int/en/>.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT), Lower Limb Activity Data, Physiotherapy Exercises, Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs).

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

To be decided.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo.

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Zenodo's REST API.

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Internet connection and a browser.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

The ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description,

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records,

<https://www.snomed.org/>.

ICD, International Classification of Diseases,

<https://icd.who.int/en/>

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

DataCite Schema for data description,

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.

Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate, such as general medical data format (.gdf) for recording and storing the data

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards , controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

To be decided.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

To be decided.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage

- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ThrombUS+ project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator

Role: High level management of the data set .

Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager

Role: Technical management of the data set .

Mantas Jucevičius, ThrombUS+ Project Researcher

Role: Technical management of the data set .

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

N/A

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Via publication in Zenodo.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B4 Dataset: Physiological signals and electrical impedance plethysmography measurements collected from thrombolytic DVT patients and healthy volunteers

Electrical impedance plethysmography and ECG measurements and a set of labels for each set of measurements, including participant demographics, collected from 20 patients during catheter-directed thrombolysis and 20 healthy volunteers.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational

Experimental Derived or Compiled

Electrical impedance plethysmography signals, electrical impedance plethysmography parameters, ECG signals, patient demographics and biometrics

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Electrical impedance plethysmography signals (csv, MATLAB file)
- Electrical impedance plethysmography parameters (PDF)
- ECG signals (ASCII file).
- Patient demographics and biometrics in a Word document (.docx)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Less than 10GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

Training AI Models.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected from 20 thrombolytic DVT patients and 20 healthy volunteers.

- Data from healthy volunteers collected in Health and Assistive Technology Laboratory at Tampere University.
- Data from DVT patients in Tampere University Hospital.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

For metadata only.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will be available via Zenodo and follows the DataCite's Metadata Schema.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

DataCite Schema for data description

(https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCiteMetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf)

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records

(<https://www.snomed.org/>)

ICD, International Classification of Diseases

(<https://icd.who.int/en/>)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description

(https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCiteMetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf)

SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records

(<https://www.snomed.org/>)

ICD, International Classification of Diseases

(<https://icd.who.int/en/>)

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT), Electrical Impedance Plethysmography (EIP), Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP), Lower Limb

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

None

Dataset stored locally or internal network drive.

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Impedance and venous occlusion plethysmography signals during catheter-directed thrombolysis for the assessment deep vein thrombosis.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The study's privacy policy does not allow publication or sharing of the data. Patient data is difficult to anonymize due to the small number of potential participants. Since patient data cannot be published, the entire dataset will keep closed.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During the project: Access is restricted to research group members.

After the project ends (or a maximum of 10 years after the study): The dataset will be anonymized and archived in the Tampere University. Access will remain restricted due to the sensitive nature of the dataset.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Pseudonymized data is stored in electronic form for a maximum of 10 years. After that the data is anonymized and archived in Tampere University.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite provides relevant fields

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite Schema for data description:

<https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/>

DataCiteMetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

N/A

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Using common standards and format where appropriate.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Dataset is for internal use only, not publicly licensed

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved by local by the local ethical review board of the Wellbeing Services County of Pirkanmaa and the national competent authority of Finland, Fimea.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Other

Other: Logs of investigational devices and data collection activities, clinical investigation monitoring.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

N/A

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Antti Vehkaoja (ORCID: 0000-0003-3721-3467)

Professor, Leader of Sensor Technology and Biomeasurements Group (Tampere University), GA member in the ThrombUS+ project

Role: High level management of the dataset .

Sami Maja (ORCID: 0009-0009-9052-3780)

Researcher in Sensor Technology and Biomeasurements Group (Tampere University), project team member in the ThrombUS+ project

Role: Technical management of the dataset .

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Passwords
- Other

Other: Data are pseudonymized and thus collected without directly identifying information.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

Data access: Access are restricted to research group members.

Data storage: The data are stored in pseudonymized form on the researcher's computers or internal network drives, protected with a username and password.

Data sharing: The data are not shared.

Data recovery: Data are stored on several researcher's computers and internal network drive, which enables backup .

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Pseudonymized data is stored in electronic form for a maximum of 10 years. After that, the data will be anonymised and archived in Tampere University.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data sharing restricted by the Data Protection Act (Tietosuojalaki 1050/2018) of Finland and GDPR. The study's privacy policy also restricts data sharing. The study for data collection has been approved by the local ethical review board of the Wellbeing Services County of Pirkanmaa and the national competent authority of Finland, Fimea.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary

- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Privacy policies
- National laws

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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